

The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Job Performance through the mediating role of Job Involvement

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Abstract

The various employee working attitude in an organization are imperative in attaining organizational goals. Job satisfaction and job involvement are some of the major indispensable working attitudes that used to excel job performance and organizational performance. The objective of this research is to see the effect of job satisfaction on employee job performance through the mediating role of job involvement taking Gondar city administration municipality office as a case study. Explanatory research is the research design used to meet the research objectives. Gondar city administration municipality office is selected purposively by the researcher due to its relevance in promoting good governance in the city administration. To know the effect of job satisfaction and job involvement on the job performance of employees, employees in the municipality office and in the six sub-cities were participants of this study. The study took 312 employees who are currently working in six sub-cities and the municipality office using census method to determine the sample size of the study. After checking multiple linear regression assumptions, data analysis is performed and the result shows that job satisfaction and job involvement have a positive moderate and strong significant effect on employee's job performance respectively. The research result also found job satisfaction has a positive moderate effect on employee's job involvement. The mediation analysis result shows that job involvement partially mediate the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance. The statistical result of this study revealed that job involvement is better than job satisfaction in predicting job performance. Therefore, according to the result, it is possible to conclude that job satisfaction has less level of effect on job performance. In excelling the job performance of employees, public service provider organizations including Gondar city municipality office should introduce human resource practices that increase the levels of employee's job satisfaction and job involvement and hence improve their motivation to higher performance.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Job Involvement, Job Performance, Employee, Municipality, Gondar city

1. Introduction

Every organization whether it is public or private could not achieve its objective without their employees. Employees are the main reason that an organization could exist for a long time. In this sense, understanding and utilizing the implications of the connection can increase satisfaction and involvement as well as performance which both are beneficial to employers and their employees (Günay, 2018). As we know, job satisfaction plays a vital role in life of man, because it affects positively on the personal and social adjustment of the individual. On the country, job dissatisfaction adversely effects on the physical and mental health of the individual. The relationship between job satisfaction and employees performance has always been discussed in organizational behavior and human resource management literature. A highly satisfaction employee need not necessarily be a profound performer (Yanchovska, 2021).

Extensive evidences revealed that in the developed nations, job satisfaction and job involvement are the two most observed popular areas that have concerned significant attention in public and private organizations (Girma, 2019). This is because of the fact that devoted and joyful workforce will contribute towards organizational performance in general and for individual job performance in particular. The relationship between job involvement, job satisfaction and job performance is well studied concept in western organizational literature because job satisfaction and job involvement are crucial factors having direct effect over organizational performance in general and employee job performance in particular. It is generally assumed that since workers with high job satisfaction and job involvement are usually highly satisfied with their organization and job, hence puts extra efforts to perform better in the organization which ultimately leads to organizational efficiency. Job satisfaction is the act of integration among employees' needs and their professional values (Inayat & Khan, 2021). In another definition job satisfaction can be seen as an improvement and stability in job in terms of environment and personality standardization (Shmailan, 2016). According to Robbins & Judge (2013), job satisfaction is a positive feeling about one's own current job results from an evaluation of its characteristics. According to these scholars, high level of job satisfaction creates positive feeling in employees whilst low level of job satisfaction leads to negative feelings. In addition, it is observed from the

previous studies that when an employee is satisfied, he/she will perform at his/her level best to achieve the organizational objectives (Jan & Subramani, 2016). Employees who are highly satisfied are usually regular and punctual, more productive, more committed, and more satisfied in their lives (Bakotić, 2016). In this context, to boost the level of job satisfaction in order to improve performance, employees should be given the opportunities of advancement, i.e., pay scales, participation of employee in policy making, and taking efforts to increase organizational commitment (Danish et al., 2015).

The Job Involvement of the individual seems to be potentially fundamental to the satisfaction of certain salient psychological needs that could lead to positive organizational implication (Gopinath & Kalpana, 2020). Job Involvement is the degree to which an employee identifies with his job, actively participates in it, and considers his job performance important to his/her self-work (Robbins & Judge, 2013). Nowadays, organizations whether they are public and private have started to analyze their human resource. Motivated employees are vital role in an organization. Due to motivation, job Involvement is peremptory for productivity to achieve the organizational goals. Job Involvement is strongly influenced by the perception towards work. Job Involvement is more associated with psychological identification of worker's opinion on job. While morale in Job Involvement refers to the position of the staff of the organization which is a collective concept, Job Satisfaction is the sense of individual employee (Fernández-Salineró et al., 2020).

Currently, job involvement has attracted attention as a key contributing factor to an organization's success. According to Bagia et al. (2020), job involvement is seen as means of aiding productivity and creating work situations in which individual and organizational goals are integrated. This involvement leads to enhanced satisfaction and increased productivity for the organization. Job involvement has also been reported to be a top organizational priority as fostering employee involvement can enhance an organizational effectiveness and success.

Conducting a research in terms of the effect of organizational behavior variables is the most relevant and popular topic in organizational behavior and psychology (Jan & Subramani, 2016). In this context, Mazayed et al. (2014) in their study on the impact of attitude on employee performance suggested that it is important to identify the variables associated with the employee work related attitude and organizational performance. Organizations are in existence to succeed

and the achievement of the strategy through individual output places the attention directly on performance (Haile, 2019). According to Khan & Akbar (2014), effective management of job performance through developing positive work-related attitude is critical if the goals and objectives of the organization are to be achieved.

As it is indicated above, great concern of organizational topics that related to attitude and behavior such as job involvement, job satisfaction and job performance has been initiated by its potential benefits to individuals and organizations. This is because satisfied, committed and involved employees are unlikely to indicate low performance and are normally highly productive for the achievement of organizational goals and organizational values (Girma, 2019).

Job satisfaction, job involvement and job performance are three key variables that are impacted the overall success of an organization (Mazayed et al., 2014). Hence, the present study was planned to explore the effect of job satisfaction on employee job performance through the mediating role of job involvement taking Gondar city municipality office of Gondar city administration as a case study.

Many studies are conducted in the world on the effect of employee job satisfaction on employee job performance; the effect of employee motivation on job performance; the relationship between organizational behavior and job performance. Besides, too limited studies have been conducted on the effect of job satisfaction on employee job performance through the mediating role of job involvement. Most of existing studies were undertaken in the developed and developing countries context. To the best knowledge of the researcher, no study was conducted in the Ethiopian context in general and Gondar Municipality office of Gondar city administration context in particular. In this regard, different researchers suggested that it is important to determine whether the concepts and conclusions regarding work related attitude such as job satisfaction, job involvement, organizational commitment and performance hold true in cultural context. Since most of the studies in the area are focused on other countries' context, this research is interested to carry out the study on Municipality office in Gondar city, Ethiopia.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

1.1.1. General Objective

The general objective of the study was to examine the effect of job satisfaction on employee job performance through the mediating role of job involvement in Gondar city municipality office.

2. Review of Theoretical Concepts

2.1 Definition and Concepts of Job Performance

It is obvious that, performance is something that is individual because each employee has a different level of ability to do their jobs. Performance depends on the combination of ability, effort, and opportunity obtained. Employee performance is capital for companies to survive and develop in responding to business and business competition today, advanced and developing companies are very dependent on reliable human resources so that the output is high performance on employee performance which will later affect the company's performance (Inuwa, 2016).

Recognizing the performance of each employee is essential as the crucial management decisions are based on individual performance (Justina & Benjamin, 2020), leading to an organizational success. Performance is defined as "behavior that accomplishes results" (Armstrong & Taylor, 2014). Individual job performance is defined as "things that people actually do, actions they take, that contribute to the organization's goals". Furthermore, according Inayat & Khan (2021) job performance is made up of all work related behavior. In addition, job performance is the accomplishment of those tasks that comprise a person's job (Bashir et al., 2020). It means execution of total set of job related tasks. The tasks that should be performed are different from one job to another.

In addition to the above concepts, employee's performance has been defined as work performance in terms of quantity and quality expected from each employee (Abba, 2019). With increase in competition, firms have recognized the importance of the employee's job performance to compete in this global market because as the performance of the employees increases, it will affect firm's performance and ultimately profitability of the firm (Dizgah et al., 2012). Every employee working within the organization is expected to perform his or her job in a dependable way. He or she is responsible for successful performance of tasks and duties

involved in the job according to the employment contract. Employees accept certain job assignments and agree to do them dependably.

Many previous studies have been examined two types of individual job performance. According to Kappagoda (2012), the first one is task performance or the in-role performance. And the second one is contextual performance or the organizational citizenship behaviors (OCBs). The concepts of these two types of individual job performance further defined by Borman and Motowidlo (1993) cited in (Alromaihi et al., 2017). They further explained, task performance involves the effectiveness which employees perform the activities that are formally part of their job and contribute to the organization's technical core and studied that appropriate performance referred to those behaviors that maintained the vast social environment in which the technical core must function. It included more unrestricted behaviors that assisted the organizations to function. On the other hand, contextual performance comprises organizational activities that are volitional, not prescribed by the job, and do not contribute directly to the technical core. Contextual performance includes activities such as helping, cooperating with others, and volunteering, which are not formally part of the job but can be important for all jobs (Alromaihi et al., 2017).

2.1.1 Definition and Concepts of Job satisfaction

It's crucial to the management in order to improve organizational overall performance to understand job satisfaction (Yuspahruddin et al., 2020). The definition of Job satisfaction is described by many authors. Some of the common definition that has been used by those authors have discussed below.

Different scholars have been made a huge contribution in defining job satisfaction and suggests important professional guidance in a time when job satisfaction research was in its early stages (Ali & Ashraf, 2021). In this sense, Hoppock (1935) as cited in (Aziri, 2011) was one of the firsts who brought the term job satisfaction in to attention. He defined job satisfaction as "any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause a person truthfully to say I am satisfied with my job". Job satisfaction was defined by Locke (1976) as cited in (Girma, 2019) as "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job and job experiences". Saiyadain (2009) as cited in (Alromaihi et al., 2017) defined Job satisfaction as the "End state of feeling". He further explained, the Feelings could be either positive or negative depending on whether needs are satisfied or not. Job satisfaction is "a

positive feeling about a job, resulting from assessing and evaluating its characteristics” (Robbins & Judge, 2013). People, who have positive feelings about their job, hold a high level of job satisfaction, while People, who have negative feelings about their job, hold a low level of job satisfaction (Robbins & Judge, 2013). Armstrong & Taylor (2014) defined Job satisfaction as “the attitudes and feelings people have about their work”. They stated that the indication whether a person is satisfied or dissatisfied depends on his attitude toward his job, a person who feels and think positively toward his job, then he’s satisfied and vice versa. It is crucial to understand and recognize the human element in any organization. A successful organization usually sees an average worker as the root source of quality and productivity gains (Kedir et al., 2021). Such organizations do not look to capital investment, but to employees, as the fundamental source of improvement.

Furthermore, according to Topa (2020), job satisfaction is considered as one of the main factors that affect efficiency and effectiveness of business organizations. Now days“ organizations and managements are concentrating on employees“ wellbeing and focusing on understanding their wants, needs, personal goals and desires. Satisfied employee is a happy employee and a happy employee is a successful employee (Günay, 2018). The importance of job satisfaction specially emerges to surface if had in mind the many negative consequences of job dissatisfaction such a lack of loyalty, increased absenteeism, increase number of accidents etc. (Aziri, 2011). Job

satisfaction has significant effect on organizational measures, such as customer satisfaction and financial measures. Hence achieve organizational success and competitiveness (Shmailan, 2016).

2.2 Definition and Concepts of Job Involvement

Job involvement is a process by which an employee identifies his job to be actively involved in it and considers important performance that is beneficial to him. This is supported by the opinion of Bagia et al. (2020) who reveal that “job involvement represents the extent to which an individual is personally involved with his or her work role”. In addition, the same thing was also expressed by Topa (2020) who said that “job involvement is the degree to which a person identifies with his or her job, actively participates in it, and consider his or her performance important to self-worth”. On the other hand, Agusramadani et al. (2018) also revealed that job involvement is a form of commitment of an employees in involving the role and concern for work both physically, knowledgeably and emotionally and considers the work he does is very important and has a strong belief to be able to complete it. From the opinions of the experts above, it can be concluded that the job involvement the same of the employee participation in a role and care for his job both physically, knowledgeably and emotionally and considers the work he does is very important and has a strong belief to be able to complete it. Including the involvement or participation of employees in making decisions and solving problems related to work improvement, such as improving quality, making decisions productively, using efficient work method, increasing safety, and employee retention (Aleinein, 2016).

According to Robbins & Judge (2013) job-involvement is the degree to which a person identifies with one’s job, actively participates in it, and considers performance important to self-worth. Furthermore, Gopinath & Kalpana (2020) explain that job involvement is the extent of one’s own identification with one’s jobs. People with high level of job involvement consider their jobs as an important part of their life. Khan & Akbar (2014) argue that job involvement in this modern economic era is specifically responsible to the availability of human resource. Kisaka et al. (2019) states that job involvement is the internalization of the value of the goodness of job or the

importance of one's job for one's value. Job involvement as the level of job performance influences one's pride and the level on how one's physiologically identifies oneself as with the job or the importance of the job for the total image of oneself. Abdallah et al. (2017) states that job involvement is the level where one attached oneself to the job and actively participating within, and also consider performance is important for one's pride. Employees' involvement is a participative process using the whole of work capacity of the employee and designed to increase employee's commitment for the sake of company's success. Moreover, Justina & Benjamin (2020) explains that job involvement may indicate the degree of integration of the employees and the company since the more integrated company and employees is in line with the time spent by the employees at work.

2.3 Review of Empirical Evidences

How employees feel and behave in an organization is very important in determining how they will perform any assigned task. As such, employee attitude has been at the center stage of human resource management strategies as a means to improving their performance and commitment to their job and by extension the performance of the organization (Soale & Akudugu, 2021). In this regard, this study was tried to assess the effect of job satisfaction on employee job performance through the mediating role of job involvement. To understand their individual links, reviewing of previous studies are vital. Therefore, the following section tried to discuss the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance as well as the relationship between job involvement and job performance.

2.3.1 Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Job Performance

Extensive evidences revealed that job satisfaction can be explained as a general attitude towards one's job (Sait, 2017). Job satisfaction is the difference between the amount of rewards workers receive and the amount they believe they should receive. The speculation that job satisfaction is related to performance dates back to the early days of the field of Industrial/Organizational Psychology and there were a complex relation between job satisfaction and performance (Soale & Akudugu, 2021). Job satisfaction is important because it displays demonstrated relationship to performance and value preferences. Many researchers have carried out various studies to examine the relationship between job satisfaction and employee's job performance. Individuals with higher job satisfaction perform better, and organizations with more satisfied employees tend to be more effective than those with fewer (Robbins & Judge, 2013).

Previous studies conducted by Bekele (2020); Haile (2019); Jan & Subramani (2016); Rahiman & Kodikal (2017); and Soale & Akudugu (2021) concluded that there is positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance. Moreover, Assalf (2015) and Bako (2008), in a study aimed at finding the relationship between satisfaction, attitude and performance suggested that there is a strong positive relationship between job satisfaction and performance of employees. They further elaborate their finding as “If one person is happier with his designation, salary and job, working hours it means he/she is satisfied, and satisfaction leads to good performance. Similarly, other previous studies also suggested that there is a significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance (Getahun, 2020; Widjajani et al., 2017).

2.3.2 Relationship between Job Involvement and Job Performance

Job involvement is one of the most studied employee attitudes in organizational research. Job involvement has attracted attention as a key contributing factor to an organization’s success (Abdallah et al., 2017). Bagia et al. (2020) defined been defined as the degree to which a person psychologically identifies or committed to his/her job. Job involvement of employees contributes to determining the success and failure of the organizations. Thus, organizations focus on improving the job involvement of the employees to achieve the organizational goals and objectives (Fernández-Salineró et al., 2020).

In this context, several previous studies revealed that job involvement highly contributes to enrich the job performance of employees (Jan & Subramani, 2016; Nasir et al., 2011; Rahiman & Kodikal, 2017; Soale & Akudugu, 2021). Widjajani et al. (2017) stated that, people who are high in job involvement genuinely care for and are concerned about their work. Many studies suggest that job involvement has a positive relationship with organizational commitment and job satisfaction (Gopinath & Kalpana, 2020; Justina & Benjamin, 2020; T. I. Khan & Akbar, 2014; Kisaka et al., 2019; Robbins & Judge, 2013). Furthermore, different studies revealed that, job involvement leads improve the organizational citizenship behavior, emotional attachment to the organization, voluntary actions beyond the job description, and participation in organizational decisions, but also reduces the desire to leave the job (Agusramadani et al., 2018; Aleinein, 2016; Bagia et al., 2020; Fernández-Salineró et al., 2020; Qureshi et al., 2019; Yvonne et al., 2014). These, factors are considered as the critical elements to enhance the job performance of employees. Moreover, researchers suggested organizations need to turn their focus on enhancing

the job involvement to increase the employee productivity which turns leads to enhance their job performance (Oravee et al., 2018; Rizwan et al., 2011) Thus, job involvement considered as the critical work related attitude of employee which highly contributes to enhance the employees' active and conscious participation in the organizational activities to improve the employees' job performance and overall organizational performance. Similarly, Jan & Subramani (2016) further stated that there is a significant and positive relationship found between job satisfaction and employee performance. In addition, there is a significant and positive relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance. They further reported that the job performance of the employee depends on their attitude towards the work and organization. If the work related attitude of the employees are positive i.e. more satisfied in their job, more involvement towards the job, which in turn improves efficiency, then more committed towards the organization, obviously which will result in better job performance. Therefore, based on the above cited literature evidences, it can be possible to establish a positive relationship between job involvement and job performance of employee. According to the above literature, this review establishes that job involvement has a positive relationship with job performance.

2.3.3 The effect of Job Involvement on Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is one of the main interests in the field of organizational behavior and the practice of human resource management. Job satisfaction is the result of Job involvement and organizational commitment. When employees involve their work, satisfaction occurred (Gopinath & Kalpana, 2019). They further discovered that job involvement and organizational commitment have been acting as important factors that contribute to job satisfaction. According to Gopinath (2021), the satisfied employee contributes, his best in the organization, in turn the contribution influences the performance and output of the organization. Performance is the factor which determines the career promotion and financial benefits of academic leaders, a whole employee's psychological association with the organization which otherwise called job involvement found enhanced. Furthermore, a study conducted by Khan & Nemat (2011) revealed that job involvement has a significant impact on medical doctors' satisfaction working at Teaching Hospitals of Riphah International University in Pakistan. This study has empirically demonstrated that job involvement has a positive relationship with the level of job satisfaction among the selected sample of doctors. Similarly, Gopinath (2020) argued that job satisfaction is also significantly and positively related to organizational commitment and work job

involvement. This indicates that higher level of job satisfaction results to higher level of organizational commitment and work job involvement. Additionally, job satisfaction has greater effect on organizational commitment than job involvement.

Extensive studies were conducted to study the role of job involvement, job satisfaction and organizational commitment in organization. From those researchers we can clearly understand that these factors are interdependent. For example, the studies of Gopinath & Kalpana (2020) revealed that job satisfaction and job involvement are depending each other, one may not exist without other. It is proved by the study of Roswandi et al. (2021) with the result significantly indicates that job involvement has a direct effect on job satisfaction. They further concluded that there is a positive relationship between job involvement and intrinsic job satisfaction, there is no significant relationship, yet there is a positive relationship between job involvement and extrinsic job satisfaction (Roswandi et al., 2021).

Moreover, Gopinath & Kalpana (2019) stated that job involvement have a positive relationship and an explanatory power for job satisfaction. Family planning field workers should have high job involvement since it has a positive direct impact on job satisfaction. Family Planning field workers that are actively involved in their work drive job satisfaction. Based on the description aforementioned, it is suspected that high job involvement has a direct impact on the Family Planning field workers' job satisfaction (Roswandi et al., 2021). And also, a study by Nwankwo et al. (2014) indicates that there is a significant relationship between the level of job satisfaction and the level of job involvement of employees. This is because an increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees will also lead to an increase in also the level of job involvement and also the possibility of staying or continuing in the same organization by the employee. In other words, employees' have a significantly related degree of job satisfaction and job involvement as Secondary School Teachers in IhubeOkigwe, Imo State in Nigeria. In addition, according to some other studies, Abdallah et al. (2017); Gopinath & Kalpana (2019); K. Khan & Nemati (2011); Nwankwo et al. (2014); and Yuspahruddin et al. (2020) job involvement has a positive relationship with the level of job satisfaction among the selected sample of different employees. This indicated that job involvement positively and significantly affects job satisfaction and organizational commitment. It is known that a high level of job involvement can increase the quality and quantity of work results and eventually lead to job satisfaction.

2.4 Mediating Effect of Job Involvement in the Link between Job Satisfaction and Performance

The levels of competition among private companies and public organizations nowadays have intensified even further. Companies compete not only with domestic entities but with international and global companies as well. In view of this, there is this never-ending pursuit of that competitive advantage a company can utilize to stay at least a step ahead of competition. Many others have looked at developing superior and more technologically advanced products while other have looked in improving their services. But no matter what strategy a company employs, there will always be a need for them to have good employees. Good, motivated, satisfied, involved and committed employees. Without this, nothing can ever be accomplished. In this sense, this section tried to discuss the mediating effect of employee's job involvement on the link between job satisfaction and performance. As a result, a few studies have been done in the past wherein job involvement was used as a mediating and moderating variable. For example, Mendoza (2019) conducted a study which focused on the mediating role of job involvement between job satisfaction and organizational commitment in a small and medium sized business enterprise. Hence, the results of his study showed that job satisfaction is a good predictor of organizational commitment. And also, the results showed that job involvement can be a significant mediator between job satisfaction and organizational commitment. In view of the above results, managers should always find ways on how their employees can achieve job satisfaction since based on the model presented; job satisfaction is the prelude in achieving job involvement and organizational commitment. It can be posited that employees lacking organizational commitment might be a symptom of lack of job involvement or more so lack of job satisfaction (Mendoza, 2019). Moreover, a study conducted by Gopinath (2020a) pinpointed that the mediation effect of job involvement between self-actualization and job satisfaction is partial as the indirect effect to get reduced but remains significant. Similarly, Gopinath (2021) stated that with mediating variable job satisfaction has direct positive effect on organizational commitment ($\beta = .42, p < .001$) and job involvement ($\beta = .38, p < .001$). These results indicate that job satisfaction significantly mediated the effect of self-actualization on academic leader's organizational commitment and job involvement. In addition, he further argued that job satisfactions have greater effect on organizational commitment than job involvement. This implies that job satisfaction mediated the effect of self-actualization to organizational

commitment and job involvement. The effect of self-actualization to organizational commitment and job involvement is greater when the academic leaders are satisfied. Moreover, Culibrk et al. (2018) reported that job involvement mediates the influence of job satisfaction on organizational commitment, but this is a partial mediation and a major part of the effect of satisfaction on the organizational commitment is achieved directly.

2.5 Conceptual framework

Source: Adopted from Rizwan et al. (2011)

NB: The figure represents the relationship between job satisfaction and job involvement towards job performance and job involvement as a mediator between job satisfaction and job performance.

1. Research Methodology

1.1. Research Design and Approach

The study was intended to explore the effects job satisfaction on employee's job performance through the mediating role of job involvement. The study was applied explanatory research design to examine the effect and relationship among the variables. Purpose of this study is hypotheses testing, since this research study was conducted to investigate the effects job satisfaction on employee's job performance through the mediating role of job involvement of Gondar city administration Municipality Office. Studies that engage in hypotheses testing usually explain the nature of certain relationships, or establish the differences among groups or the independence of two or more factors in a situation (Kothari, 2004). The type of this study was correlational. Correlational research is used to examine a relationship between two or more concepts (Walliman, 2011). Correlational research enables the researcher to understand the relationship between the independent variables (Job Satisfaction and Job Involvement) and dependent variable (job Performance). Correlation analysis was used to determine the direction and strength of effect and relationship between these variables. Regression analysis was also run to look at the predictive ability of job satisfaction and job involvement on job performance. Besides, the mediating role of job involvement between job satisfaction and job performance through regression model was conducted. The planned study was cross sectional in time and the unit of analysis in this research was individuals as the data was collected from the employees working in the Municipality of Gondar city administration.

With regards research approach, the study was employed a quantitative approach by which data was collected through self-administered questionnaire. According to Creswell (2014), quantitative data is advantageous in its relative precision and lack of ambiguity. Typical forms of quantitative research are surveys, in which many respondents are asked questions and their answers are averaged and other statistical calculations; and research based on administrative data is counted (Kothari, 2004). Quantitative research is also an approach for testing theories by examining the relationship among variables (Creswell, 2014). The rationale for using quantitative approach is that it best fits for the data collection instrument (questionnaire) which is was selected by the study. Furthermore, quantitative approach is useful as it enables the researcher to collect objective and numerical data which is simple to apply statistical tools and to examine the relationship between variables. These variables, in turn can be measured, typically on

instruments, so that numbered data can be analyzed using statistical procedures.

1.2. Population of the Study

The general source of population for the study was Gondar city administration Municipality office including the six sub-cities employees who are working in the respective sub-cities municipality office. Employees of the Municipality including managerial and department leader staff members was population elements. Kothari (2004) observe that a population is the total collection of elements about which one wants to make inferences. In this sense, the target population for the study was all the employees of the Municipality and the six sub-cities namely: Azezo-Tseda, Fasil, Maraki, Zobil, Jantekel and Arada. Hence, the target population was 312 employees working at the Municipality and the six sub-cities (Municipality office report, 2023). In line to this, all employees of the targeted organization was considered by the study. Therefore, the target population for the study from which the sample was drawn is all staff member of the selected organization.

1.3. Sampling Technique and Sample Size Determination

Regarding the study context, the researcher purposefully selected Municipality Office, one of the public institution in Gondar City Administration. The study organization is considered as one of the strategic office that provides basic services to its customers and it is vital in promoting good governance in the city administration.

With respect to sample size determination, the current study employed the census method. Therefore, all the employees (312) were taken as the sample size of the study.

1.4. Data Source and Data Collection Techniques

The data used in this study was primary data which was collected from sample members through closed questionnaires with 1-5 Likert Scale (1= Strongly Disagree and 5= Strongly Agree). The structured questionnaire was circulated by the researcher through the welfare officers of the selected organization. Initially, the questionnaire is prepared in the English language and translated to Amharic to make it understandable and convenient to all the employees of the organization.

Measurement of Dependent and Independent Variables

1.4.1.1. Measurement of Dependent variables

Job performance as a dependent variable was selected to study how it is impacted by the independent variables in the present study. The operationalization and measurement of this dependent variables is dealt below.

Job Performance

Job performance was operationalized as quantity and quality expected from each employee in their job. Job performance can be divided in to two, task and contextual. Task performance comprises of job explicit behaviors which includes fundamental job responsibilities assigned as a part of job description. Contextual performance is a kind of pro-social behavior demonstrated by individuals in a work set-up. Job performance was measured with the help of scale developed by Pradhan and Jena (2016). This instrument was consisted of different statements and the responses was collected on a five point continuum namely, strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree.

1.4.1.2. Measurement of Independent Variables

Keeping the objectives of the investigation in view, two independent variables viz. job satisfaction and job involvement was selected and measured as detailed below.

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the amount of pleasure or contentment associated with a job. Based on this, job satisfaction was measured with the help the nine dimension of scale developed (Spector, 1985). This instrument was consisted of different statements and the responses was collected on a five point continuum namely, strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree.

Job Involvement

Job involvement is the willingness of a person to work hard and apply effort beyond normal job expectations. It was measured with the help of scale developed by (Lodahl & Kejner, 1965). This instrument was consisted of different statements and the responses was collected on a five point continuum namely, strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree.

1.5. Data Analysis Method

Data collected through questionnaire was analyzed and interpreted quantitatively which was further be organized and treated with different statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency count, percentages was calculated to the demographic characteristics of respondents. The data were entered into SPSS version 25 in order to draw simple tabulations to describe the demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Pearson correlation was used in order to explain the relationship between the variables, dependent (job performance) and the independent (job satisfaction and job involvement).

Pearson correlation allow how well variables are related, their strength and direction of the linear relationship. In addition, multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the level of effect of job satisfaction and job involvement on employee job performance. Similarly, the mediating role of job involvement between job satisfaction and job performance through regression model was conducted.

Results and Discussion of the findings

1.1. Introduction

This part provides detail outlines about both the Inferential and hypothesis testing results of the findings. It also presents the reliability and correlation result analysis of the study variables. Finally, this chapter discussed about the assessment of the measurement model, evaluation of the structural model and hypothesis testing of the study.

1.1. Correlation Result Analysis

Person correlations coefficient was calculated to find the association among variable. The result of the association of the study variables under investigation is presented below.

Table 4.11: Correlation Analysis Results

Variables	JS	JI	JP
Job Satisfaction	1		
Job Involvement	.443**	1	
Job Performance	.450**	.516**	1
Source: Own Survey Data, 2023; **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). JS=Job Satisfaction; JI= Job Involvement and JP= Job Performance			

Table 4.11 shows the person correlation coefficient matrix of the different variables. In order to discuss the strength of the association among the study variables, the value of correlation strength developed by Cohen (1988) was presented as follows (see table 4.12).

Table 4.12: Degree of Correlation and the Value of r

S/No.	Type of correlation level	r-value	Significance
1	No Correlation	$< \pm 0.01$	No Significance
2	Small Correlation	± 0.10 to 0.29	Weakly Significance
3	Medium Correlation	± 0.30 to 0.49	Moderately Significance
4	Larger Correlation	± 0.5 to 1.00	Strongly Significance

As it is illustrated in table 4.11 above, the finding of the correlation analysis revealed that association was existed between predictor variables (job satisfaction and job involvement) and the outcome variable (job performance) at 0.001 level of significance. For example, job satisfaction ($r= 0.450$, $p<0.001$) is moderately correlated with job performance. It is also observed that job involvement ($r= 0.516$, $p<0.001$) has strong association with job performance. In comparison with the Cohen's degree of correlations, it was ensured that the association of the study variables ranges from moderate to strong association between the independent variables and the dependent variable. On the other context, regarding the correlation of the independent variables among each other, the finding of the correlation analysis demonstrated that there is presence of association between the independent variables. In this sense, job involvement ($r= 0.443$, $p<0.001$) has moderately associated with job satisfaction.

2.1. Multiple Regression Analysis

2.1.1. Regression Results

The coefficient statistics is used to see the contribution of individual predictors on the outcome variable. It is also helpful to understand the directional effect of the relationship between the variables, whether it is positive or not. In this sense, the value in the column titled *Sig (P value)* explains whether the predictor is significant or not in predicting the outcome variable.

The coefficient table below (Table 4.16) illustrates the coefficient values with beta, t-values and significant values of the predictors on job performance. It is through the coefficient table that we came to know the predictive values of job satisfaction and job involvement on job performance. Look at the beta value and this tells if the regression is positive or negative for these variables. The *b*-values tell us about the relationship between the predictors (job satisfaction and job involvement) variables with the outcome variable (job performance). From the table we

understand that job satisfaction have positive moderate relationship with job performance, but job involvement has positive high relationship with job performance of employee's. Therefore, the analysis shows that job satisfaction and job involvement did significantly predict job performance at the $p < .001$ level ($b = .393$, $t(288) = 5.091$, $p = .000$) and $p < .001$ level ($b = .506$, $t(288) = 7.301$, $p = .000$) respectively.

Table 4.16: Regression Statistics of the Model

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	7.534	4.445		1.695	.091		
1 JS	.393	.077	.275	5.091	.000	.803	1.245
JI	.506	.069	.394	7.301	.000	.803	1.245

a. Dependent variable: JP (Job Performance)

JI (Job Involvement) and JS (Job Satisfaction)

Source: Own Survey Data, 2023

The individual contribution of variables to the regression model is found in the Coefficients table from SPSS output as can be seen in the above table. From the coefficient table job satisfaction with ($b = .393$) indicates that as the value of job satisfaction increases by one unit, job performance of employees also increases by 0.393 unit (when there is a one percent increase in job satisfaction, employees job performance increases in 39 percent). This interpretation is true only if the effect of job involvement is held constant. Similarly, job involvement with ($b = .506$) indicates that as the value of job involvement of employees increases by one unit, job performance of employees also increases by 0.506 unit (when there is a one percent increase in job involvement, employees job performance increases in 51 percent). This interpretation is true only if the effect of job satisfaction is held constant. From these beta values job involvement of employees has a better effect on job performance of employees than job satisfaction.

T tests helps to conceptualize as measures of whether the predictors are making a significant contribution to the model. Therefore, if the *t*-test associated with a *beta* value is significant (if the value in the column labelled *Sig.* is less than .05) then the predictors are making a significant contribution to the model (Field, 2009). The smaller the value of *Sig.* (and the larger the value of

t), the greater the contribution of that predictor is. In this sense, for this model, job satisfaction and job involvement $t(288) = 5.091, p = .000$ and $t(288) = 7.301, p = .000$ respectively are significant predictors of job performance of employees.

2.2. Hypothesis Testing

The contribution of the independent variables on the outcome variable is clearly indicated in the regression result (table 4.16). Other things constant, the beta coefficient (regression weight) is the average amount of the dependent variable increases when the independent variables increases by one standard deviation. Hence, the two independent variables (job satisfaction and job involvement) contribute significantly at 5% level of significance.

Hypothesis 1: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on job performance of employees

It was proposed that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee's job performance. Thus, the finding of the regression analysis revealed that job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.393, p < .05$). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. The meaning of this finding is that, employee's satisfaction in their job can increase the job performance of Gondar city administration municipality office employees. Consistent with this findings, previous studies conducted by Bekele (2020); Haile (2019); Jan & Subramani (2016); Rahiman & Kodikal (2017); and Soale & Akudugu (2021) argued that job satisfaction has positive effect on employee job performance. Similarly, Bakan et al. (2014) reported similar result that job satisfaction has a positive impact on job performance and occupational commitment. These proved that employees with high satisfaction do perform better and contribute to the overall success of an organization. Moreover, this study findings is consistent with the findings of (Hettiararchchi & Jayarathna, 2014; Inayat & Khan, 2021b; Saleem & Imran, 2014; Shmailan, 2016). On the contrary, a study by Matagi et al. (2023) argued that there is no significant relationship and effect between job satisfaction and employees job performance.

Hypothesis 2: Job involvement has a positive and significant effect on job performance of employees

The second hypothesis was about a positive and significant effect of job involvement on job performance. The multiple regression analysis revealed that job involvement ($\beta = 0.506, p < .05$) has a significant and positive effect on job performance, supporting for the hypothesis. The result

of this study confirmed that job involvement has statistically significant relation and effect on job performance of employees than job satisfaction. This reflects employees of a given organization who are psychologically identified or committed for his/her job has become performed better than the non-engagement employees. The more the employees are involved in their job the more they perform better and achieve their organization goal.

Many previous research works ensure that employees job involvement significantly supports for better employees job performance and nothing is especial for this research it is also consistent with prior works in the area. The involvement of employees in their job is so important in the public service organization especially the municipality office where a large number of urban residents are waiting there to get the service. The result of this research, positive effect of job involvement on employees job performance, is consistent with the work of Matagi et al. (2023) found that job involvement has significant effect on employees job performance. It is also similar with the work of Johari & Yahya (2019); Kasaya & Munjur (2018); and Thevanes & Dirojan (2018) job involvement has significant effect on employees job performance. Furthermore, this findings is also similar with the works of Odero & Makori (2017) argued that employee involvement had a great influence on employee performance. On the other hand, a study by Prasetyo et al. (2021) argued that job involvement has a significant influence on work engagement, but job involvement has no significant influence on employee performance.

2.3. Multiple Linear Regression Output for the Effect of Job Satisfaction on Job Involvement

Assessing the level of effect of job satisfaction on job involvement is the objective of the study. This objective is intended to explore whether job satisfaction has a major effect on job involvement of employees. By doing so, job satisfaction was checked whether it has relationship and predictive value on employee's job involvement.

Therefore, this part is going to show statistically how employee's job satisfaction could put effect on job involvement of employees. Multiple Linear regression analysis was conducted to understand the effects of job satisfaction on job involvement.

The Pearson's r correlation between the predictor variables (job satisfaction) with job involvement was conducted. Table 4.17 below show that there is a positive moderate correlation between job satisfaction and job involvement, $r(288) = .443, p < .001, n = 290$.

Table 4.17: Correlations between Job Satisfaction and Job Involvement

	Job Satisfaction	Job Involvement
Job Satisfaction	1	
Job Involvement	.443**	1
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)		

Source: Own Survey Data, 2023

A multiple linear regression was conducted to see if job satisfaction has effect and predictive value on job involvement of employee"s. The three tables below (model summary, ANOVA and coefficient) show how the independent variables predict the dependent variable. Using the enter method of multiple linear regression, Table 4.18 (model summary table) under this table SPSS tells us what the dependent variable (Job Involvement) was and what the predictors was also (job satisfaction).

It was found from table 4.18 that job satisfaction explain the variance in the value of job involvement ($F(1,288) = 70.444, p < .001, R^2 = .197, R^2_{adjusted} = .194$). The R^2 indicates how much the variability in the outcome (job involvement) is accounted by employee"s job satisfaction. The model explains 20% of the variability on job involvement is explained by job satisfaction.

Table 4.18: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.443 ^a	.197	.194	9.93243	1.850

a. Predictors: (Constant), JS (Job Satisfaction)

b. Dependent Variable: JI (Job Involvement)

Source: Own Survey Data, 2023

The fit of the regression model can be assessed using the model summary and ANOVA table. ANOVA tests whether the model is significantly better at predicting the outcome than using the mean as a „best guess“ (Field, 2009). Table 4.19 (ANOVA table) demonstrates this reality, there is a significant effect of job satisfaction on job involvement $F(1,288) = 70.444, P = .000$. As it is shown below the F -ratio is significant to predict the model. Thus, employee"s job satisfaction

has a significant effect on employee's job involvement (the outcome variable). Its independent effect is shown on the coefficient table.

Table 4.19: Model Fitness Result Analysis (ANOVA^a)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6949.527	1	6949.527	70.444	.000 ^b
	Residual	28412.091	288	98.653		
	Total	35361.617	289			

a. Dependent Variable: JI (Job Involvement)

b. Predictors: (Constant), JS (Job Satisfaction)

Source: Own Survey Data, 2023

The coefficient table below (Table 4.20) illustrates the coefficient values with beta, t-values and significant values of the predictor on job involvement. It is through the coefficient table that we came to know the predictive values of job satisfaction on job involvement. Look at the beta value and this tells if the regression is positive or negative for these variables. The *b*-values tell us about the relationship between the predictor (job satisfaction) variable with the outcome variable (job involvement). From the table we understand that job satisfaction has positive moderate relationship with job involvement. Therefore, the analysis shows that job satisfaction did significantly predict job involvement at the $p < .001$ level ($b = .494$, $t(288) = 8.393$, $p = .000$).

Table 4.20: Regression Statistics of the Model (Coefficients^a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	39.932	2.955		13.514	.000
	JS	.494	.059	.443	8.393	.000

a. Dependent Variable: JI (Job Involvement)

Source: Own Survey Data, 2023

The individual contribution of variables to the regression model is found in the Coefficients table from SPSS output as can be seen in the above table. From the coefficient table job satisfaction with ($b=.494$) indicates that as the value of job satisfaction increases by one unit, job involvement of employees also increases by 0.494 unit (when there is a one percent increase in job satisfaction, employees job involvement increases in 49 percent).

T tests helps to conceptualize as measures of whether the predictors are making a significant contribution to the model. Therefore, if the *t*-test associated with a *beta* value is significant (if the value in the column labelled *Sig.* is less than .05) then the predictors are making a significant contribution to the model (Field, 2009). The smaller the value of *Sig.* (and the larger the value of *t*), the greater the contribution of that predictor is. In this sense, for this model, job satisfaction *t* (288) =8.393, $p=.000$) is significant predictor of job involvement of employees.

Hypothesis 3: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on job involvement of employees

In this study, job satisfaction was proposed to have a positive and significant effect on brand job involvement. As it was expected, the finding of this study demonstrated that job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.443$, $p < .05$) have a positive and significant effect on job involvement (table 20). This shows that the proposed hypothesis is accepted. The research result confirmed that job satisfaction has a moderate positive relationship with job involvement. The meaning of this finding is that, employee's satisfaction in the working environment can increased the involvement of employees in their job of Gondar city administration municipality office.

Consequently, this result is consistent with the findings of Culibrk et al. (2018) who reported that there is strong connection between job satisfaction and job involvement. Similarly, a study by Jose & Panchanatham (2014) found similar result with the current study. They stated that employees with high levels of job involvement identify with and care about their jobs, whereas, employees with high levels of affective commitment feel positively about their organization and wish to remain a member in it where they feel jobs satisfied. They also argued that high job involvement leads to high job satisfaction. Job involvement is how people see their jobs as both a relationship with the working environment, the job itself and how their work and life are commingled. Job satisfaction and job involvement are correlated with one another. This argument is supported by Khan & Nemati (2021) that job involvement has a significant impact

on medical doctors" satisfaction working at Teaching Hospitals of Riphah International University of Pakistan. Moreover, this findings also supported by the findings of Agusramadani et al. (2018) and Safaria & Rahmatullah (2016) who argued that job satisfaction affects significantly the employees job involvement. On the contrary, this findings is inconsistent with the findings of Gupta & Prasad (2020) who argued that there is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and job involvement of library professionals of Himachal Pradesh University of India.

2.4. Mediating Role of Job Involvement

Another important objective of this research and its statistical results discussed here is the mediating role of job involvement between job satisfaction and job performance. The direct effect of predictor variable on the outcome variable is also discussed because it is one precondition that should be fulfilled for mediation to happen. At this juncture the indirect effect of job satisfaction on job performance through job involvement (mediator) is presented.

This section of the analysis demonstrates the mediation analysis among variables. In general, a given variable may be said to function as a mediator to the extent that it accounts for the relation between the predictor and the criterion (Ackerman & Henson, 2015). Taking in to account this definition a relationship between the predictor and outcome variable is established with the inclusion of external (mediator) variable that would enhance the relationship. In this sense, this analysis is devoted to see whether Job involvement mediates the relationship between job satisfaction (predictor variable) and job performance (criterion variable).

A necessary component of mediation is a statistically and practically significant indirect effect (Preacher & Hayes, 2004). The type that occurs when one variable (M) mediates the effect of X on Y we term this model simple mediation. The simple relationship between X and Y is often referred to as the *total effect* of X on Y . we denote the total effect c to distinguish it from c' , the *direct effect* of X on Y after controlling for M . (Preacher & Hayes, 2004).

The formal heuristic analysis often used to detect simple mediation effects is straightforward and follows directly from the definition of a mediator provided by Baron and Kenny (1986). A variable functions as a mediator when it meets the following conditions

(1) X significantly predicts Y (i.e. $c \neq 0$) or when path a and b are controlled, a previously significant relation between the independent and dependent variables is no longer significant, with the strongest demonstration of mediation occurring when path c is zero,

(2) X significantly predicts M (i.e. $a \neq 0$) or variations in levels of the independent variable significantly account for variations in the presumed mediator (i.e., *path a*), and

(3) M significantly predicts Y controlling for X (i.e., $b \neq 0$), or variations in the mediator significantly account for variations in the dependent variable (i.e., *path b*).

Two further assumptions must be met in order to claim that mediation has occurred, according to Baron and Kenny (1986); namely, should be no measurement error in M, and Y should not cause M. These two assumptions have been met for this data. And mediation analyses are most often guided by the procedures outlined by Baron and Kenny (1986). Nothing is special for this data and it is build up on this model.

2.4.1. Mediating Role of Job Involvement between Job Satisfaction and JobPerformance

This section discussed the mediating role of job involvement between job satisfaction and job performance. The following figure shows the simple mediation i.e., job involvement (mediating variable), job satisfaction (predictor variable) and job performance (outcome variable).

Panel A

Panel B

Figure 1: **Panel A:** illustration of total effect, job satisfaction affects job performance. **Panel B:** illustration of a mediating design job satisfaction affects job performance indirectly through job involvement.

This model adapted from (Hayes, 2023) assumes a three-variable system such that there are two causal paths feeding in to the outcome variable: the total impact of job satisfaction on job performance (path c) the direct impact of the independent variable job satisfaction on job performance (*path c'*) and the impact of the mediator job involvement on job performance (*path b*). There is also a path from the independent variable job satisfaction to the mediator job involvement (*path a*). The statistical result below demonstrates whether above proposed mediation model is significant or not. The analysis was done using (Hayes, 2023) process macro plug version 4.1 in tool it is easy to run the mediation analysis. A macro is a program that will run when a shortcut command is given to execute it. Rather than running the entire program for each analysis. For mediation to happen the following preconditions should be fulfilled.

1. X variable (job satisfaction) predicts Y variable (job performance) – path c
2. X variable (job satisfaction) predicts M (job involvement) – path a
3. X (job satisfaction) and M (job involvement) together predicting Y (job performance)
 - a. M variable (job involvement) predicts Y (job performance) – path b
 - b. X variable no longer predicts Y or is lessened predicting y – path c'

The process macro plug in regression output is provided below to see whether the above preconditions of mediation are fulfilled or not. Each requirement for mediation analysis is discussed separately.

Run MATRIX procedure:

Model: 4

Y: Job Performance

X: Job Satisfaction

M: Job Involvement

Sample size=290

3.1.Recommendations

After analyzing the outcome of the survey analysis, the study has recommended some of the strategies which might be effective in improving employee's job performance.

- The municipality office in particular and public service provider organizations in general

should introduce human resource practices that increase the levels of employee's job satisfaction and job involvement and hence improve their motivation to higher performance. In particular issues like creating healthy relationships between co-workers as well as the relation between management and workers, developing the competence of the supervisor and workers, creating opportunities for employees to achieve their personal goals and facilitating channels to employee suggestions should be explicit elements of human resource management activities.

- Performance standards should be established with the participation of employee representatives and communicated to all members. Employees who are reaching standards and or above standard should be recognized and rewarded. This will create sense of belongingness and ownership to the values and goals of the organization. This also motivates employees to achieve the standards and perform well
- Periodical employee's job involvement as well as job satisfaction survey should be employed by the municipality office and public service provider organization in order to measure the level of employees job satisfaction as well as job involvement and accordingly immediate response should be given to the problems occurred by discussing with employees through creating employees voice channel.
- The municipality office and public service provider organizations should focus on the strategies by which they can develop positive work related attitudes to gain from employees' performance. A good positive work related attitude driving packages like good compensation packages, conducive working conditions and equipment's, opportunity for training and promotion should be in place in order to get the reflection of positive attitudes and improved employee performance.
- Public service provider organizations and the municipality office should pay attention to their employees' job satisfaction levels as determinants of their performance, turnover, absenteeism, and withdrawal behaviors. To raise employee satisfaction, they should evaluate the fit between the employee's work interests and the intrinsic and extrinsic parts of the job then create work that is challenging and interesting to the individual.
- As the job involved employees put extra efforts for the completion of their task, these employees become involved in the work not only physically but also emotionally and cognitively. Therefore, service provider organizations should design jobs in a way that reflects the positive feeling of employee.

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